

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ROTATORY
POWER ON CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART XVII.
NITRO- AND CARBOXY- ARYL DERIVATIVES OF
STEREOMERIC METHYLENECAMPHORS.

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The present communication is a continuation of Parts XII, XV and XVI and describes the optical rotatory dispersion of the condensation products of oxymethylenecamphors (*l*-, *d*-, *dl*-) with nitroanilines (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-) and aminobenzoic acids (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-).

p-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor was prepared according to the method of Pope and Read (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 171) and the melting point was found to be identical with that recorded by these authors. This does not agree with that of either of the two forms *viz.* α -form, m.p. 180-81° and β -form, m.p. 151-52° isolated by Rupe and collaborators (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, **3**, 50). The latter authors do not, however, record any rotatory power data. Pope and Read give the rotation of the dextro compound as $[\alpha]_{\text{Na}_D}^{20} = 356.9^\circ$ in benzene; whereas we get $[\alpha]_{\text{Na}_D}^{35} = 331.2^\circ$ (Table XV).

m-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor was also prepared according to the method of Pope and Read (*loc. cit.*) and it melts at 181° instead of 167-68° as recorded by these authors. Our observed value of rotation $[\alpha]_{\text{Na}_D} = 249.6^\circ$ in benzene (Table VII) differs from those *viz.* 269.2° (initially) and 233.9° (after 24 hours) given by the above authors. Our compound, however, does not exhibit any mutarotation, a fact which goes against the observation and conclusion of these authors.

o-Carboxyanilinomethylenecamphors (*d*- and *l*-), prepared by us, melt at 167-68° and differ from either of the two forms of the same compound *viz.* α -form (m.p. 176°) and β -form (m.p. 112°) isolated by Rupe and collaborators (*loc. cit.*). The authors, however, do not record any rotatory power data,

TABLE A.

Compounds.	$[\alpha]_{\text{H}_g}^{35^\circ}$ green					
	MeOH.	EtOH.	Acetone.	Pyridine.	CHCl ₃ .	C ₆ H ₆
*Anilino-M	480.0°	451.3°	448.9°	433.2°	424.6°	367.1°
$i.e., \text{C}_8\text{H}_{14} \begin{cases} \text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{NH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11} \\ \text{CO} \end{cases}$						
* <i>m</i> -Toluidino-M	454.4	439.9	442.3	405.8	384.8	352.6
* <i>p</i> -Toluidino-M	465.0	440.8	425.8	401.6	401.6	355.4
† <i>o</i> -Chloroanilino-M	400.2	405.8	380.0	391.3	386.6	364.7
† <i>m</i> -Chloroanilino-M	388.5	384.7	388.0	374.4	381.4	363.6
† <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino-M	417.7	406.3	401.8	394.4	374.6	359.4
‡ <i>o</i> -Bromoanilino-M	347.5	339.9	330.1	328.4	329.0	314.3
‡ <i>m</i> -Bromoanilino-M	—	354.0	348.4	334.3	324.1	279.3
‡ <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino-M	361.1	355.6	360.6	348.8	324.3	291.9
‡ <i>m</i> -Iodoanilino-M	328.5	319.5	309.7	294.8	279.1	251.1
‡ <i>p</i> -Iodoanilino-M	338.1	325.9	326.5	318.4	300.0	258.6
<i>o</i> -Nitroanilino-M	**493.1	—	**468.1	**424.8	**484.6	399.2
<i>m</i> -Nitroanilino-M	393.9	—	389.2	367.1	350.0	315.6
<i>p</i> -Nitroanilino-M	510.7	—	519.4	545.0	493.5	437.0
<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenylamino-M	388.9	388.5	373.5	377.5	382.2	395.6
<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenylamino-M	396.8	390.9	376.1	371.5	—	—
<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenylamino-M	—	—	—	426.3	—	—

* Singh, Bhaduri and Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 345.† Singh and Bhaduri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 340‡ Singh and Bhaduri, *ibid.*, 1939, 10A, 359

** Extrapolated values from the equations.

Effect of Chemical Constitution on the Rotatory Power.—Since polar effect of a substituent group is traceable in optical activity (Singh and Bhaduri, Parts XV and XVI; Betti, *Gazzetta*, 1923, 53, 424) we

should expect that the substitution of positive groups such as NO_2 and COOH in anilinomethylenecamphors will increase the rotation of the parent compound, and the effect would be most marked in the case of *ortho*-substituents owing to the close proximity of the substituent group. The nitro substituent in the *ortho* and *para* positions has the maximum rotation amongst the series of substituent groups so far examined (*cf.* Table A) and the rotation in the *meta* position is intermediate. The position of COOH group is anomalous; in the sequence of substituent groups, as a positive group, it ought to be in the proximity of NO_2 , another strongly positive one. But it is always intermediate in the series, with no fixed position. Except in benzene in the case of *ortho*-substituents, nowhere is the polar sequence strictly followed; the position of COOH -group being most uncertain of the series. A similar irregularity is observed in the position of the COOH -group amongst the different groups of the "molecular inductive capacity" series (Rule and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2188).

Nature of the Solvent and Rotatory Power.—There is no regular sequence of the solvents although in previous communications it was observed that the sequence of the solvents with reference to optical rotation was more or less similar to that of their dielectric constants.

Position Isomerides and Rotatory Power.—The sequence of the rotatory power of the position isomerides of nitroanilinomethylenecamphors is in general $p > o > un > m$ in all the solvents. This is neither in agreement with Frankland's lever arm hypothesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1583) nor with the electrostatic modifications suggested by Rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1122) as according to either of the two, *meta* should be always intermediate between *ortho* and *para*. A similar line of discussion may be extended to the position isomerides of carboxyanilinomethylenecamphors for which the order in pyridine is $un > p > o > m$.

Physical Identity of Isomers.—The values of rotatory power of *d*- and *l*-forms in different solvents (Table I-XXVI) are identical within the limits of experimental error. Out of 195 observations now recorded, in as many as 152 cases difference in the numerical value of the specific rotatory power of the opposite isomers corresponds to a difference of less than 0.01° in the observed angle of rotation and in 36 cases the corresponding angle lies between 0.01° and 0.02° , which is the limit of experimental error allowable in such measurements. Only in 7 cases, the difference corresponds to between 0.02° and 0.03° in the observed angle of rotation. All these are, however, of the nature of casu^{al}

experimental errors. This, therefore, further supports Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry according to which the two forms, *d*- and *l*- must possess equal and opposite rotatory power.

The melting points of the racemic forms of *p*-nitroanilinomethylene-camphor and *p*-carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor are higher than those of the optically active forms. These forms are *dl*-compounds at least in the solid state.

The Nature of Rotatory Dispersion.—The compounds described in this paper obey the simple dispersion law, $[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$. In the numerical test given in the tables of rotatory dispersion [I-XXVI], this point is clearly brought out as the differences in the observed and calculated values of rotatory power lie well within the limits of experimental error.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The *laevo* and the *racemic* compounds described in the present paper were prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro* isomers and had the same crystalline form and similar solubility.

General Method of Preparation.—Oxymethylenecamphor (1 mol.), dissolved in methyl alcohol, was added to the solution of the base (1 mol.) in glacial acetic acid when a precipitate separated at once or on keeping and vigorous scratching. It was then crystallised from a suitable solvent.

o-Nitroanilinomethylene-*d*-camphor, m.p. 157-58°, was obtained as orange-red needles, easily soluble in chloroform and acetone, less so in pyridine and sparingly soluble in ether, ethyl and methyl alcohol and benzene. (Found: C, 67.98; H, 6.87. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 67.94; H, 6.71 per cent).

o-Nitroanilinomethylene-*l*-camphor melts at 158°. (Found: N, 9.40. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent). *o*-Nitroanilinomethylene-*dl*-camphor melts at 150°. (Found: N, 9.49%).

m-Nitroanilinomethylene-*d*-camphor, m.p. 181°, was obtained as bright yellow small crystals. (Found: C, 67.81; H, 6.99. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 67.94; H, 6.71 per cent). It is easily soluble in chloroform and acetone, less so in pyridine and sparingly soluble in ether, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and benzene. *m*-Nitroanilinomethylene-*l*-camphor

melts at 180-81°. (Found : N, 9.64. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent). *m*-Nitroanilinomethylene-*dl*-camphor melts at 167-68°. (Found: N, 9.48%).

p-Nitroanilinomethylene-*d*-camphor, m.p. 154-55°, was obtained as bright yellow shining needles. (Found : C, 67.96 ; H, 7.05. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 67.94 ; H, 6.71 per cent). It is easily soluble in chloroform and acetone, less so in pyridine and sparingly soluble in ether, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and benzene.

p-Nitroanilinomethylene-*l*-camphor melts at 154-55°. (Found : N, 9.47. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent). *p*-Nitroanilinomethylene-*dl*-camphor melts at 167-68°. (Found : N, 9.48%).

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*d*-camphor, m.p. 166-67°, was obtained as pale yellow rectangular plates. (Found : C, 72.01 ; H, 7.38 ; N, 4.78. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 72.24 ; H, 7.02 ; N, 4.68 per cent). It is easily soluble in chloroform, pyridine, acetone and ether, less so in benzene, ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol. *o*-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*l*-camphor melts at 167-68°. (Found : N, 4.72. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 4.68 per cent). *o*-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*dl*-camphor melts at 113°. (Found : N, 4.70%).

m-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*d*-camphor, m.p. 219-21°, was obtained as colourless needles. (Found : C, 72.02 ; H, 7.26. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 72.24 ; H, 7.02 per cent). It is fairly soluble in pyridine, less so in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and sparingly soluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. *m*-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*l*-camphor melts at 219-21°. (Found : N, 4.70. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 4.68 per cent). *m*-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*dl*-camphor melts at 215-17°. (Found : N, 4.88%).

p-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*d*-camphor, m.p. 280-83°, was obtained as long rectangular plates. (Found : C, 72.09 ; H, 7.27. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 72.24 ; H, 7.02 per cent). It is moderately soluble in pyridine and sparingly soluble in ordinary organic solvents. *p*-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*l*-camphor melts at 280-82°. (Found : N, 4.70%). *p*-Carboxyphenylaminomethylene-*dl*-camphor, m.p. 283-85°, was obtained as needles. (Found : N, 4.73%).

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2-dcm. jacketed tube at 35°. The value of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formula, is given in the tables and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.
o-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{45.54}{\lambda^2 - 0.2042}; \lambda_0 = 0.4519.$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4036	+350.6°	+1.5°	Hg ₅₇₈₀	±349.1°	+0.8°	-349.9°	0.4016
"	315.9	-1.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	317.4	-1.2	316.2	"
"	276.1	+0.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	269.4	+0.8	270.2	"
"	216.6	+0.6	Cd ₆₄₃₈	216.0	+0.6	216.6	"
"	185.8	+0.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	184.9	+0.6	185.5	"

TABLE II.
o-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{50.26}{\lambda^2 - 0.1729}; \lambda_0 = 0.4158.$$

Dextro				Laevo.			
Conc. g./100 (c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4020	+399.2°	-2.0°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±401.2°	-1.0°	-400.2°	0.4008
"	314.2	+2.4	Hg ₅₇₈₀	311.8	+1.2	313.0	"
"	288.5	±0	Na ₅₈₉₃	288.5	-0.5	288.0	"
"	250.0	-1.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	251.2	+0.7	251.9	"
"	206.4	-1.6	Cd ₆₄₃₈	208.0	-1.0	207.0	"
"	180.1	-1.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	181.5	+0.5	182.0	"

TABLE III.
o-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in methyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{57.80}{\lambda^2 - 0.1810}; \lambda_0 = 0.4254.$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	o-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4012	+378.9°	+2.9°	Hg ₅₇₈₀	±376.0°	+1.5°	-377.5°	0.4016
"	349.0	+1.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	347.4	+0.6	348.0	"
"	300.4	-2.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	302.5	-0.8	301.7	"
"	248.0	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	247.8	-0.3	247.5	"
"	215.6	+0.7	Li ₆₇₀₈	214.9	±0	214.9	"

TABLE IV.

o-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{59.07}{\lambda^2 - 0.1720}; \lambda_0 = 0.4147.$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc.	Obs. $[\alpha]$.	σ -c.	Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$.	σ '-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$.	Conc.
(g./100 c.c.)	σ .			c.		σ' .	(g./100 c.c.)
0.4020	+364.4°	$\pm 0^\circ$	Hg ₅₇₈₀	$\pm 364.4^\circ$	-0.6°	-363.8°	0.4000
"	337.0	-0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	337.5	-1.3	336.2	"
"	294.7	+0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	294.5	+0.5	295.0	"
"	243.8	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	243.6	+0.1	243.7	"
"	212.5	± 0	Li ₆₇₀₈	212.5	-1.2	211.3	"

TABLE V.

o-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{72.06}{\lambda^2 - 0.1286}; \lambda_0 = 0.3586.$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc.	Obs. $[\alpha]$.	σ -c.	Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$.	σ '-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$.	Conc.
(g./100 c.c.)	σ .			c.		σ' .	(g./100 c.c.)
0.4000	+350.0°	-0.5°	Hg ₅₇₈₀	$\pm 350.5^\circ$	+1.2°	-351.7°	0.4024
"	330.0	+0.2	Na ₅₈₉₃	329.8	-0.5	329.3	"
"	296.2	+0.9	Li ₆₁₀₄	295.3	+0.4	295.7	"
"	251.3	-0.8	Cd ₆₄₃₈	252.1	+1.3	253.4	"
"	223.8	-0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	224.3	-0.6	223.7	"

TABLE VI.

m-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.63}{\lambda^2 - 0.1022}; \lambda_0 = 0.3196$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4028	+405.7*	-0.1*	Ag ₅₂₀₉	±405.8°	-0.5°	-405.3°	0.4036
"	350.0	-0.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	350.1	+0.4	350.5	"
"	296.7	+0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	295.9	+0.2	296.1	"
"	280.5	+0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	280.2	-0.2	280.0	"
"	254.5	+0.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	253.8	+0.2	254.0	"
"	219.8	±0	Cd ₆₄₃₈	219.8	-0.5	219.3	"
"	197.3	±0	Li ₆₇₀₈	197.3	+0.9	198.2	"

TABLE VII.

m-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{57.73}{\lambda^2 - 0.1152}; \lambda_0 = 0.3394.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4008	+401.8	-0.6°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±402.4°	+1.3°	-403.7°	0.4012
"	370.6	+0.4	Ag ₅₂₀₉	370.2	-0.1	370.1	"
"	315.6	-0.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	315.8	+0.7	316.5	"
"	314.5	+0.3	Ag ₅₄₆₆	314.2	—	—	"
"	263.2	-0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	263.7	-0.8	262.9	"
"	249.6	+0.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	249.0	-1.0	248.0	"
"	224.6	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	224.3	+0.1	224.4	"
"	193.4	+0.5	Cd ₆₄₃₈	192.9	+0.3	193.2	"
"	172.2	-0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	172.5	-0.5	172.0	"

TABLE VIII.

m-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in methyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{79.36}{\lambda^2 - 0.0974}; \lambda_0 = 0.312\mu.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α] c.	o'-c.	Laevo.	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.).	Obs. [α] o.	o-c.				Obs. [α] o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4012	+457.4°	+1.7°	Ag ₅₃₂₉	±455.7°	±0°	-455.7°	0.4024
"	393.9	-1.4	Hg ₅₄₆₁	395.3	-0.2	395.1	"
"	333.9	-1.4	Hg ₅₇₈₀	335.3	+0.2	335.5	"
"	316.5	-1.3	Na ₅₈₈₃	317.8	+0.3	318.1	"
"	289.2	+0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	288.4	-0.2	288.2	"
"	249.2	-1.0	Cd ₆₄₃₂	250.2	-0.4	249.8	"
"	225.1	±0	Li ₆₇₀₈	225.1	+1.0	226.1	"

TABLE IX.

m-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{69.80}{\lambda^2 - 0.1080}; \lambda_0 = 0.3295.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α] c.	o'-c.	Laevo.	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α] o.	o-c.				Obs. [α] o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4004	+367.1°	-0.1°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±367.2°	-0.5°	-366.7°	0.4008
"	365.9	+0.4	Ag ₅₄₆₈	365.5	+0.1	365.6	"
"	309.7	+1.0	Hg ₅₇₈₀	308.7	-0.5	308.2	"
"	291.0	-1.0	Na ₅₈₈₃	292.0	-0.3	291.7	"
"	264.7	+0.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	264.0	+0.4	264.4	"
"	228.6	+0.8	Cd ₆₄₃₈	227.8	+0.5	228.3	"
"	204.5	+0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	204.2	+0.4	204.6	"

TABLE X.

m-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{69.47}{\lambda^2 - 0.1204}; \lambda_0 = 0.3470.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4020	+461.3°	+0.8°	Ag ₅₂₀₉	±460.5°	+0.2°	-460.7°	0.4024
"	380.2	-1.4	Hg ₅₄₆₁	390.6	+0.3	390.9	"
"	388.1	-0.9	Ag ₅₄₆₈	389.0	—	—	"
"	323.3	-1.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	325.1	-0.2	324.9	"
"	307.2	+0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	306.4	-0.1	306.3	"
"	274.9	-0.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	275.5	+1.0	276.5	"
"	236.3	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	236.2	+0.4	236.6	"
"	211.3	+0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	210.8	-0.4	210.4	"

TABLE XI.

p-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.49}{\lambda^2 - 0.1476}; \lambda_0 = 0.3842.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4008	+670.1°	-0.4°	Cd ₆₀₈₅	±670.5°	-1.4°	-669.1°	0.4020
"	601.3	-0.9	Ag ₅₂₀₉	602.2	-0.3	601.9	"
"	493.5	-1.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	494.6	+0.4	495.0	"
"	397.6	-1.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	399.5	+1.0	400.5	"
"	373.1	-0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	373.4	-0.3	373.1	"
"	332.8	+1.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	331.1	-0.2	330.9	"
"	279.5	+0.5	Cd ₆₄₃₈	279.0	+0.9	279.9	"
"	247.1	+0.8	Li ₆₇₀₈	246.3	-0.1	246.2	"

TABLE XII.

p-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in methyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{77.47}{\lambda^2 - 0.1470}; \lambda_0 = 0.3834.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4004	+624.4°	+1.2°	Ag ₅₂₀₉	±623.2°	-1.9°	-621.3°	0.4008
"	510.7	-1.5	Hg ₅₄₆₁	512.2	+0.6	512.8	"
"	508.3	-1.4	Ag ₅₄₆₈	509.7	—	—	"
"	415.9	+1.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	414.1	-1.1	413.0	"
"	386.8	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	387.2	+0.9	388.1	"
"	343.9	+0.5	Li ₆₁₀₄	343.4	+0.9	344.3	"
"	289.7	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	289.6	-0.1	289.5	"
"	256.1	+0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	255.7	+0.1	255.8	"

TABLE XIII.

p-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.11}{\lambda^2 - 0.1556}; \lambda_0 = 0.3945.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4024	+720.6°	+1.6°	Cd ₆₀₈₅	±719.0°	+0.1°	-719.1°	0.4012
"	642.4	+1.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	640.6	±0	640.6	"
"	519.4	-0.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	519.7	±0	519.7	"
"	415.0	-0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	415.3	+0.9	416.2	"
"	385.2	-1.9	Na ₅₈₉₃	387.1	-0.7	386.4	"
"	340.5	-1.0	Li ₆₁₀₄	341.5	±0.0	341.5	"
"	284.5	-1.8	Cd ₆₄₃₈	286.3	+0.3	286.6	"
"	252.3	+0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	251.8	+1.2	253.0	"

TABLE XIV.

p-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{79.58}{\lambda^2 - 0.1526}; \lambda_0 = 0.3906.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4028	+671.6°	+1.2°	Ag ₅₂₀₉	±670.4°	+1.2°	-671.6°	0.4020
"	545.0	-1.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	546.7	-0.6	546.1	"
"	542.5	-1.1	Ag ₅₄₆₈	543.6			"
"	438.2	-0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	438.4	+0.6	439.0	"
"	407.9	-1.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	409.2	-1.2	408.0	"
"	361.3	-0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	361.7	+0.2	361.9	"
"	304.2	+0.3	Cd ₆₄₃₃	303.9	+0.8	304.7	"
"	268.1	+0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	267.5	-0.1	267.4	"

TABLE XV.

p-Nitroanilinomethylenecamphor in benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.05}{\lambda^2 - 0.1424}; \lambda_0 = 0.3774.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.		
0.4016	+585.2°	+0.1°	Cd ₆₀₀₅	±585.1
	529.1	+1.3	Ag ₅₂₀₉	527.8
	437.0	+0.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	436.8
"	354.8	-0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	355.0
"	331.2	-1.2	Na ₅₈₉₃	332.4
"	297.6	+1.9	Li ₆₁₀₄	295.7
"	249.0	-1.0	Cd ₆₄₃₃	250.0
	221.6	+0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	221.2

TABLE XVI.

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{69.02}{\lambda^2 - 0.1180} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3435.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs.[α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs.[α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4016	+490.6°	+0.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±490.5°	+0.7°	-491.2°	0.4000
"	449.4	-0.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	450.1	+1.1	451.2	"
"	382.2	-0.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	382.9	-0.5	382.4	"
"	318.7	-0.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	319.3	+0.7	320.0	"
"	301.3	+0.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	301.2	±0.0	301.2	"
"	270.2	-0.9	Li ₆₁₀₄	271.1	+0.2	271.3	"
"	234.1	+1.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	232.8	-0.3	232.5	"
"	207.9	±0	Li ₆₇₀₈	207.9	-1.6	206.3	"

TABLE XVII.

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.89}{\lambda^2 - 0.1165} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3413.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs.[α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs.[α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4000	+483.8°	-0.6°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±484.4°	-1.3°	-483.1°	0.4016
"	446.3	+1.4	Ag ₅₂₀₉	444.9	-2.9	442.0	"
"	377.5	-1.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	379.1	-0.6	378.5	"
"	317.5	+1.0	Hg ₅₇₈₀	316.5	-0.3	316.2	"
"	298.7	±0.0	Na ₅₈₉₃	298.7	+0.1	298.8	"
"	270.1	+1.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	268.9	+1.3	270.2	"
"	232.5	+1.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	231.2	+0.4	231.6	"
"	206.3	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	206.5	+0.2	206.7	"

TABLE XVIII.

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.39}{\lambda^2 - 0.1144} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3382.$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α] o.	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α] c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α] o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4004	+473.3°	-0.7°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±474.0°	-0.9°	-473.1°	0.4016
"	437.1	+1.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	435.9	-0.1	435.8	"
"	373.5	+1.5	Hg ₅₄₆₁	372.0	+0.4	372.4	"
"	311.0	-0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	311.3	-2.5	308.8	"
"	294.7	+0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	293.9	-1.3	292.6	"
"	266.1	+1.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	265.0	+0.3	265.3	"
"	228.6	+0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	227.9			"
"	203.5	-0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	203.8	-2.1	201.7	"

TABLE XIX.

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{70.53}{\lambda^2 - 0.1197} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3460$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α] o.	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α] c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α] o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4008	+506.5°	-0.9°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±507.4°	+0.2°	-507.6°	0.4020
"	465.4	+0.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	465.2	-1.2	464.0	"
"	395.6	+0.4	Hg ₅₄₆₁	395.2	+0.3	395.5	"
"	329.4	+0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	329.1	+0.5	329.6	"
"	309.4	-0.7	Na ₅₈₉₃	310.1	-0.4	309.7	"
"	279.5	+0.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	278.9	-0.2	278.7	"
"	239.5	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	239.3	+0.8	240.1	"
"	213.3	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	213.5	+0.5	214.0	"

TABLE XX.

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in ethyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{69.5}{\lambda^2 - 0.1199} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3463.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4004	+629.4°	+0.3°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	±629.1°	—	—	0.4000
"	502.0	+1.3	Cd ₅₀₈₅	500.7	-0.7°	-500.0°	"
"	458.2	-0.9	Ag ₅₂₀₉	459.1	+0.8	459.9	"
"	388.5	-1.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	389.7	+0.3	390.0	"
"	324.7	+0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	324.5	+0.5	325.0	"
"	304.7	-1.2	Na ₅₈₉₃	305.9	+1.6	307.5	"
"	273.5	-1.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	275.1	-1.4	273.7	"
"	236.0	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	235.9	+0.4	236.3	"
"	211.1	±0.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	211.1	-0.2	211.3	"

TABLE XXI.

o-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in methyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{69.45}{\lambda^2 - 0.1204} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3470.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. [α]. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α]. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α]. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4024	+503.2°	+1.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±502.1°	+0.2°	-502.3°	0.4012
"	459.7	-0.6	Ag ₅₂₀₉	460.3	+0.9	461.2	"
"	388.9	-1.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	390.5	-0.4	390.1	"
"	324.3	-0.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	325.0	+0.3	325.3	"
"	306.9	+0.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	306.3	+0.3	306.6	"
"	274.6	-0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	275.4	+0.1	275.5	"
"	236.1	-0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	236.2	-0.6	235.6	"
"	211.2	+0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	210.7	±0.0	210.7	"

TABLE XXII.

m-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{67.57}{\lambda^2 - 0.1163} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3410.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c	Obs. $[\alpha]$ o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4024	+593.9°	+1.6°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	± 592.3°	—	—	0.4012
"	474.4	-0.1	Cd ₅₀₈₅	474.5	-2.1°	-472.4°	"
"	436.1	+0.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	436.0	+0.3	436.3	"
"	371.5	± 0.0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	371.5	-0.1	371.4	"
"	310.6	+0.4	Hg ₅₇₈₀	310.2	+0.1	310.3	"
"	293.2	+0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	292.8	+0.2	293.0	"
"	263.4	-0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	263.7	-0.7	263.0	"
"	227.4	+0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	226.7	+0.2	226.9	"
"	202.5	± 0.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	202.5	-0.5	202.0	"

TABLE XXIII.

m-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.3}{\lambda^2 - 0.1165} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3413.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4028	+600.9°	+1.4°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	± 599.5°	—	—	0.4016
"	480.4	+0.1	Cd ₅₀₈₅	480.3	+0.4°	-480.7°	"
"	441.9	+0.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	441.2	+0.8	442.0	"
"	376.1	+0.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	375.9	+1.4	377.3	"
"	314.8	+1.0	Hg ₅₇₈₀	313.8	+1.2	315.0	"
"	295.4	-0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	296.2	-1.1	295.1	"
"	266.9	+0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	266.7	-1.4	265.3	"
"	229.7	+0.5	Cd ₆₄₃₈	229.2	-0.1	229.1	"
"	204.8	± 0.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	204.8	-0.6	204.2	"

TABLE XXIV.

m-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in ethyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{70.33}{\lambda^2 - 0.1180} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3435.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. $[\alpha]$. o.	o-c.			o'-c	Obs. $[\alpha]$. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4016	+499.2°	-0.5°	Cd ₅₈₈₅	± 499.7°	+0.3°	-500.0°	0.4020
"	458.1	-0.5	Ag ₅₂₀₉	458.6	+0.4	459.0	"
"	390.9	+0.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	390.2	+0.3	390.5	"
"	324.9	-0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	325.4	+0.5	325.9	"
"	307.5	+0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	307.0	-1.0	306.0	"
"	276.5	+0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	276.3	-0.1	276.2	"
"	237.8	+0.6	Cd ₆₄₃₈	237.2	-0.8	236.4	"
"	211.6	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	211.8	+1.0	212.8	"

TABLE XXV.

m-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in methyl alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{70.62}{\lambda^2 - 0.1202} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3467.$$

Dextro.			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$. c.	Laevo.		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. $[\alpha]$. o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$. o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4020	+509.9°	+0.1°	Cd ₅₈₈₅	± 509.8°	-0.6°	-509.2°	0.4016
"	466.3	-1.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	467.3	+0.9	468.2	"
"	396.8	± 0.0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	396.8	+0.4	397.2	"
"	329.6	-0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	330.1	+1.1	331.2	"
"	310.9	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	311.3	-0.1	311.2	"
"	279.9	+0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	279.8	-0.9	278.9	"
"	241.3	+1.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	240.0	+0.3	240.3	"
"	213.9	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	214.1	± 0.0	214.1	"

TABLE XXVI.

p-Carboxyphenylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.78}{\lambda^2 - 0.1229}; \lambda_0 = 0.3506.$$

Dextro.				Laevo.			
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)	Obs. [α] o.	o—c.	Line.	Calc. [α] c.	o'—c.	Obs. [α] o'.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.)
0.4000	+550.0*	-0.8*	Cd ₅₀₈₅	± 550.8	-1.2*	-549.6*	0.4012
"	505.1	+1.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	503.9	-1.6	502.3	"
"	426.3	-0.4	Hg ₅₄₅₁	426.7	-0.4	426.3	"
"	353.8	-0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	354.1	-0.1	354.0	"
"	335.0	+1.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	333.6	+0.5	334.1	"
"	300.0	+0.5	Li ₆₁₀₄	299.5	-2.8	296.7	"
"	256.3	-0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	256.4	+0.4	256.8	"
"	228.8	+0.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	228.7	+0.6	229.3	"

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